

RAISING MANPOWER FOR THE HOTEL INDUSTRY

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Hotel is a major establishment over the years, that has been able to cater for the housing necessity of visitors on a short term basis while hospitality is a broad category of field within the service industry that includes lodging, restaurants, event planning themes park and transportation. This study determined the hospitality provided by some hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State. One hundred and twenty respondents (100 customers and 20 members of staff) were selected from the hotels using systematic and random sampling techniques. Five research questions were formulated for the study. The instrument used for data collection was a validated structured questionnaire and data collected were analyzed using frequency counts and simple percentage. Major findings showed that (30% and 45%) staff and customers responded that the major categories of hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State are suite hotels. Staff (20% and 20%) responded that good security and television in the room were facilities provided by their hotel respectively. Customers (25% and 21%) responded that parking space and televisions in the room were facilities provided by the hotels respectively. Staff and customers (30% and 27% respectively) responded that job opportunity to the people of the society, followed by sources of accommodation for the travelers (25% and 24% respectively) were the relevance of hotel industry in Ondo town. It was recommended that hotelier should improve their services by providing breakfast, laundry services, saloon and gymnastic centre for their customers.

Keywords: Human Capital, Human Capital Development, Firm and Firm Performance.

Introduction

Hotel is a French word meaning host which referred to a French version of a town house or any other building where visitors are seen frequently rather than a place offering accommodation. In contemporary French usage, hotel now has the same meaning as the English term and hotel particularly is used for the old meaning (Hoshi, 2011).

Hotel is a major establishment over the years that have been able to cater for the housing necessity of visitors on a short term basis. The provision of basic accommodation, in time past, consisting only of a room with a bed, a cupboard, a small table and wash stand has largely been replaced by rooms with modern facilities including en-suite bath rooms and air

conditioning or climate control. Additional common features found in hotel rooms are telephone, an alarm clock, a television, a minibar with refrigerator and facilities. Luxury features include bath robes, slippers and Jacuzzi bathtubs. Larger hotels may provide additional guest facilities such as swimming pool, fitness centre, business center, internet facility, child care, conference facilities and social function services (Marriott, 2003).

Hotel is a commercial establishment providing lodging, meals and other guest services (Hoshi, 2011). Hotels are classified into several categories, as there is no standard method of assigning these ratings and compliance with customary requirements is voluntary. Hotel rooms are usually numbered (or named in some

smaller hotels) to allow guests to identify their rooms. Some hotels offer meals as part of a room and board arrangement. In the United Kingdom, a hotel is required by law to serve food and drinks to all guests within certain stated hours. In Japan, Capsule hotel provides a minimized amount of room space and stored facilities.

The hospitality industry is a broad category of fields within the service industry that includes lodging, restaurants, events planning, theme parks, transportation and cruise line. Additional fields within the tourism industry are several billion dollars industry that mostly depends on availability of leisure time and disposable income. A hospitality unit such as a restaurant, hotel or even an amusement park consists of multiple groups such as facility maintenance, direct operations (servers, house keepers, porters, kitchen workers, bartender, etc), management marketing and human resources.

The hospitality in hotel is seen to be a very important aspect in any hotel set up. It is the vision of every hotel manager to satisfy the yearnings and aspirations of their customers, who come visiting their hotel for one reason or the other. Hospitality in hotels is based on the size, function and cost of such hotel.

Most hotels and major hospitality companies that operate hotels have widely accepted industry standard to take care of their customers. Every hotel has its major target which is customers, their hospitality is the hotel's major concern. The major mission and goals of a hotel is to provide the finest facilities and service in the market while providing a good place to work for its employees and a reasonable return for the investments by its owner. Most hotel statement should address three major constituents which are the guest, hotel management and the employee (Bovin, 2012).

Establishment of hotels in a particular area provides various opportunities and boosts the economic activities of this particular area. Among the benefits of hotel is the provision of job opportunity, Naom, (1999) There are various department and section in hotels that

contributed their quote while rendering service to the consumer. All these departments section can only function with the help of competent and hardworking personnel. A hotelier can not single handedly work alone in an hotel. He has to employ labours to various departments of the hotels. By so doing he has been able to reduce the rate of unemployment by providing job opportunities to people. These people will be able to increase their standard of living.

The establishment of hotels has helped in generating revenue for the hoteliers and the government. The main reason of establishing a business firm is to maximize profit (Bank 2000). Hotels provide accommodation, catering and laundry services. Some hotels have sports facilities, such as basket ball and tennis courts. Some hotels also have internet facilities and board conference halls, etc.

The hotelier generates revenue for himself and his own profit and in maintaining the sustainability of the hotel. Hotels also generate revenue for the government through taxation. All hotels in Nigeria are expected to pay their annual or monthly tax to the government. The Government also sees hotel as a source of revenues in hospitality industry. This is the reason why the government also establishes and control some hotels by himself, for instance, Owena Motel in Alagbaka, Akure is owned by the Ondo State Government.

The researcher noticed that most hotels in Ondo town lack adequate facilities and services for operation. This could be one of the reasons why only a few of them are regularly patronized by customers. Therefore, this research work was carried out to find out about the hospitality industry, its problems, and solutions such as suggesting the raising of manpower for the hospitality industry in the Local Government Area, State and Nigeria as a whole...

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate hotel hospitality in Ondo town, Ondo State. Specifically, the study:

- i. identified the different types and classification of hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State.
- ii. determine the facilities provided by hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State.
- iii. identified the services provided by the hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State.
- iv. determine the problems facing hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State.
- v. identified the relevance of hotel industry in Ondo town, Ondo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide this study:

- i. What are the different types and classification of hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State?
- ii. What facilities are provided by hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State?
- iii. What are the different types of services provided by hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State?
- iv. What are the problems facing hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State?
- v. What is the relevance of hotel industry in Ondo town, Ondo State?

Research Methodology

Research Design

The design that was used for this study was the descriptive survey design. The design was adopted because descriptive studies make no attempt to manipulate variables, as such it is concerned with describing and interpreting existing relationships, attitudes, practical processes and trend as well as comparing variables.

Area of the Study

The study was carried out in Ondo town, Ondo state. There are twenty hotels in Ondo town. They were put into three groups based on the

physical facilities, geographical location, internet facilities and structure of each hotel

Population of the Study

The hotel staff and customers that patronize selected hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State constituted the population for the study.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

For the purpose of this study simple random sampling technique was adopted. Ten hotels were selected randomly by balloting. As can be seen above, the hotels in Ondo town were classified into three groups. The hotels in each of these groups was assigned number which was written on pieces of paper, wrapped and arranged in a container i.e. a container was used for each group. Three hotels were selected from each of the groups, one and two. For hotels were selected from group three. Ten customers and two members of staff were randomly selected in the selected hotels to make a total of one hundred and twenty respondents.

The selected hotels were:

1. Day Love Hotel
2. Blue Roof Hotel
3. Exporter Hotel
4. R.K.Y Hotel
5. Sunny Sky Hotel
6. Top Most Hotel
7. Love and Peace Hotel
8. Olamojiba Hotel
9. Stella Pallace Hotel
10. Tumapo Tupado Hotel

Research Instrument

A structured questionnaire was used to collect data for the study. The questionnaire was administered to the staff and customers of the selected hotels. The questionnaire consisted of two sections (A and B). Section A consisted of personal data of the respondents and section

consisted the test items based on the objectives of the study.

Validation of Instrument

The questionnaire was subjected to face validation by three lecturers in the Department of Home Economics to ascertain that the instrument would solicit the information required within the frame of the research questions.

Method of Data Collection

One hundred and twenty copies of questionnaire were administered by the researcher to twelve randomly selected

respondents from each out of the ten selected hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State (i.e. customers and two staffs). Literate customers and staff filled the questionnaire themselves while the researcher filled them for the illiterate customers and staff. Completed questionnaire was collected immediately by the researcher.

Method of Data Analysis

The responses of the questionnaire were analysed through the following data analysis techniques;

- i frequency count
- ii simple percentage

Presentation and Analysis of Data

Results

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of respondents

1.1: Percentage distribution of respondents on sex

Gender	Staff		Customers	
	Frequency	Percentage %	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	8	40	73	73
Female	12	60	27	27
Total	20	100	100	100

Table 1.1 above shows that 60% of the staff and 27% of customers were females while 40% of the staff and 73% of customers were males.

This implies that majority of the staff were female and majority of customers were male.

1.2: Percentage distribution of respondents' educational status.

Qualification	Staff		Customers	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
M.A/M.Sc	2	10	25	25
B.A/B.Sc	4	20	18	18
NCE	5	25	16	16
ND	3	15	14	14
SSCE	3	15	12	12
JSSCE	2	10	5	5
Modern III	1	5	10	10
Total	20	100	100	100

The table above shows that, 25% of the staff were N.C.E holders, 20% were B.A/B.Sc holders, 15% and 15% were ND and SSCE holders respectively, 10%, 10% and 5% were holders of JSSCE, M.A/M.Sc and Modern III certificate respectively. 25%, 18%, 16%, 14%,

12%, 10% and 5% of customers were holders of M.A/M.Sc, B.A/B.Sc, N.C.E., ND, SSCE, Modern III and JSSCE. This implies that many of the staff respondents were NCE and M.A/M.Sc (25% and 20% respectively). Many of the customers (25% and 18% respectively)

ed here M.A/M.Sc and B.A/B.Sc holders respectively.

en 13: Percentage distribution of staff on the numbers of rooms in their hotels.

S/N	Number of Rooms	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Below 150 rooms	12	60
2.	150 to 299 rooms	8	40
3.	300 to 600 rooms	0	0
4.	More than 600 rooms	0	0
	Total	20	100

as The above table shows that, most of the hotels (60%) in Ondo town, Ondo State have below 150 rooms, 40% have 150-299 rooms. No hotel

is in Ondo town has 300-600 and above 600 rooms. This implies that majority of hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State have below 150 rooms.

Research Question 1: What are the different types and classification of hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State?

Table 2: Types of hotels and their classification

S/N	Types of Hotels	Staff		Customers	
		F	%	F	%
A	Business hotel (for business travelers)	4	20	20	20
B	Suite hotel	6	30	45	45
C	Apartment hotel: (it provide long-term accommodation)	2	10	11	11
D	Resort hotels (usually located in the mountains)	1	5	8	8
E	Bed and breakfast hotels (these are house with rooms converted into overnight facilities)	0	0.0	0	0
F	Extended base hotel (offers kitchen amenities in the rooms, these hotels are for travellers who want to stay more than a week)	4	20	9	9
G	Conference centre (it focus on meetings and conferences)	3	15	7	7

Data in table 2 above shows that 30%, 20%, 20%, 15%, 10% and 5% responded that the hotels were suite, business, extended base, conference centre, apartment and resort hotels respectively. 45%, 20%, 11%, 9%, 8% and 7% of customers responded that the hotels were

suite, business, apartment, extended base, resort and conference centres respectively. Highest respondents of staff and customers (30% and 45% respectively) responded that the hotels were suite followed by business (20% and 20% respectively).

Research Question 2: What facilities are provided by hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State?**Table 3: The facilities that are provided by hotels in Ondo Town**

S/N	Facilities	Staff		Customers	
		F	%	F	%
A	Parking space for customers	3	15	25	25
B	Good security for customers	4	20	15	15
C	Conducive environment for customers	2	10	10	10
D	Swimming pool	3	15	9	9
E	Television in rooms	4	20	21	21
F	Air conditioners in rooms	3	15	14	14
G	Lawn tennis courts	1	5	6	6

Data in table 3 above shows that 20%, 20%, 15%, 15%, 15%, 10% and 5% of the staff responded that good security, television, swimming pool, air conditioners in rooms, parking space, conducive environment and lawn tennis were facilities provided by their hotels respectively. 25%, 21%, 15%, 14% 10%, 9% and 6% of customers responded that the hotel has parking space, television in the rooms, good security, air conditioners,

conducive environment, swimming pool and lawn tennis courts were facilities provided by the hotels. Highest respondents of staff (20% and 20%) responded that good security and television were facilities provided by their hotel respectively. Highest respondents of customers (25% and 21%) responded that packing space and television were facilities provided by the hotels respectively.

Research Question 3: What are the different types of services provided by hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State?**Table 4: Types of services provided by hotels**

S/N	Types of Services	Staff		Customers	
		F	%	F	%
A	Full time accommodation	10	50	35	35
B	Food services	3	15	22	22
C	24 hours electricity supply	4	20	15	15
D	Laundry services	1	5	10	10
E	Bar and restaurant services	2	10	18	18
F	Breakfast	0	0	0	0

The table 4 above shows that 50%, 20%, 15%, 10%, 5% and 0% staff responded that full time accommodation, 24 hours electricity supply, food services, bar and restaurant, laundry services and breakfast were services provided by their hotels respectively. 35%, 22%, 18%, 15%, 10% and 0% of customers responded that

full time accommodation, food services, bar and restaurant, 24 hours electricity supply, laundry services, and breakfast were services provided by the hotels respectively. Highest respondents of staff and customers (50% and 35% respectively) responded that the hotels provide full time accommodation services.

Research Question 4: What are the problems facing hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State?

Table 5: The Problems facing hotels in Ondo Town

S/N	Problems	Staff		Customers	
		F	%	F	%
a	Lack of qualified staff	2	10	18	18
b	Poor services rendered	3	15	16	16
c	Lack of credibility	2	10	9	9
d	Lack of price credibility	2	10	8	8
e	Lack of innovation	3	15	19	19
f	Increase in taxation	6	30	20	20
g	Poor communication between the reservation department and other departments in the hotel	2	10	10	10

The table 5 above shows that 30%, 15%, 15%, 10%, 10%, 10%, and 10% staff responded that the problems facing hotels in Ondo town were increase in taxation, poor services rendered, stagnant innovation, lack of qualified staff, lack of credibility, lack of price credibility and poor communication between the reservation department and other departments in the hotel. 30%, 19%, 18%, 16%, 10%, 9% and 8% of customers responded that increase in taxation,

lack of innovation, lack of qualified staff, poor services, poor communication between the reservation department and other departments in the hotel and lack of credibility and lack of price credibility are the major problem facing hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State. The responses of staff and customers (30% and 20% respectively) stated that increase in taxation was the problem facing hotels in Ondo town.

Research Question 5: What is the relevance of hotel industry in Ondo town, Ondo State?

Table 6: The relevance of hotel industry in Ondo Town

S/N	Relevance	Staff		Customers	
		F	%	F	%
A	Job opportunity to the people of the society	6	30	27	27
B	Source of accommodation to the members of the society	2	10	8	8
C	Source of accommodation for the travelers	5	25	24	24
D	Increases the standard of living	2	10	10	10
E	Generate income to the government	3	15	18	18
F	Positive impact on the society at large.	2	10	13	13
Total		20	100	100	100

The table 6 above shows that 30%, 25%, 15%, 10%, 10% and 10% responded that job opportunity to the people of the society, source of accommodation for the travelers, generating income to the government, increase the standard of living, source of accommodation to the members of the society and positive impact on the society at large respectively were the relevance of hotel industry in Ondo town. 27%, 14%, 18%, 13%, 10% and 8% of customers

responded that job opportunity to the people of the society, source of accommodation for the travelers, generate income to the government, positive impact on the society at large, increase the standard of living and source of accommodation to the people of society respectively were the relevance of hotel industry in Ondo town, Ondo State. The responses of staff and customers (30% and 27% respectively) stated that job opportunity to the

people of the society followed by source of accommodation for the travelers (25% and 24% respectively) were the relevance of hotel industry in Ondo town.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the study showed that both staff and customers consider suite hotels as one and the major categories of hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State. This is in agreement with the observation of Ayoola (2008) that a suite is a kind of hotel that is the latest trend and the fastest growing segment in the hotel industry. Main attraction of these hotels is guest room with living room and a separate bedroom. In exchange for more complete living room suite hotels generally have fewer and more limited public area and guest services than other hotels. This also helps keep suite hotels guest room prices competitive in the market. Professionals such as accountants, lawyers, business men and executives find suite hotels particularly attractive as they can work and also entertain in an area besides the bedroom.

The findings revealed that staffs consider good security for customers, television in rooms and customers consider packing space for customers as the major facilities provided in the hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State. Elaine, (2012) opined that facilities that should be provided by hotel include; two sitting rooms, television room, coffee bar, safe deposit boxes, mini market, restaurant, large pool for adults, separate children pool, play ground, mini club for children, room for disable people, Balcony or terrace with a magnificent sea view, bathroom with shower or bath telephone music air conditioning hair dryer refrigerator television.

The result of data analysis in Table 4 above revealed that staff and customers consider full accommodation as major services provided by the hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State.

Kaye (2011) opined that hotel and accommodation facilities being made available at different tourist spots, have shifted focus on providing maximum comfort to tourists at reasonable rates. It is also vital to provide

comfortable accommodation to people of diverse economical backgrounds.

The findings also showed that increase in taxation is the major problem faced by hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State. It was found that the opportunity to the people of the society served by the relevance of hotel industry in Ondo town, Ondo State. In the modern times, the way people spend their vacations has undergone a great change. People like to spend good time with family and friend while at the same time exploring various tourist places across the globe. As a result the tourist industry across the globe has experienced an unprecedented growth in the hotel and accommodation facilities. Comfortable hotels and accommodation facilities play a very important role in popularizing any tourist destination (Suman, 2008). If a person, who is quite far away from home, gets the same facilities and comforts he enjoys at his home, then he is bound to become attached to the place. On the other hand if the tourist ends up at a place where the hotels and accommodation facilities are not satisfactory, it is quite likely that he might never return to that place.

Summary

This study has shown that good security and television were facilities that are provided by their hotels. Parking space and television were facilities provided by the hotels. It was found that increase in taxation was the major problem facing hotel in Ondo town. The staff and customers responded that the provision of job opportunity to the people of the society followed by source of accommodation for the travelers were perceived as the relevance of hotel industry in Ondo town.

Conclusion

- i. Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that;
- ii. Good security, television and parking space were facilities provided by hotels in Ondo town, Ondo State.

- ii. Increase in taxation was the major problem facing hotels in Ondo town.
- v. Job opportunity to the people of the society and source of accommodation for the travelers respectively were the relevance of hotel industry in Ondo town

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

- i. Hoteliers should be encouraged to recruit qualified staff. This will enable them to reach their maximum goal.
- ii. The hoteliers should be encouraged to get in more facilities such as lawn tennis, swimming pool and air conditioner into their hotels.
- iii. The hoteliers should try to improve their standard and services like having food services, laundry services, salon and gymnastic centre for their customers.
- iv. Hoteliers should try to visit other places with standard hotels to see how they render their services.
- v. Government should try to minimize their tax on hotels.
- vi. Individuals should try and have positive thought about hotels.
- vii. Hoteliers should improve their services by serving breakfast to their customers, when this is done, there is the possibility that they will have more customers to patronize them.

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